

Developing Preservice Teachers' Instructional Readiness Through Mursion Simulation Microteaching: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Effective teacher preparation requires more than theoretical knowledge; it requires opportunities for preservice teachers (PSTs) to engage in authentic, practice-based learning. This qualitative study examines the integration of *Mursion*, a mixed reality simulation platform, into the Reading Endorsement curriculum in an English Education program. Mursion provides PSTs with a virtual classroom environment where they can deliver reading-focused lessons, practice classroom management, and adapt instruction in real time with student-like avatars. Through reflective analysis and peer debriefing, this study investigates how participation in Mursion simulations supports PSTs in developing instructional confidence and responsiveness during reading instruction. The findings highlight Mursion's effectiveness in bridging the gap between coursework and live classroom experience. The simulations provide a safe and controlled environment for risk-taking, reflection, and skill development, serving as a critical transitional practicum. Implications for teacher preparation and the future of simulation-based learning are discussed.

Keywords: preservice teachers, teaching simulation, reading pedagogy, microteaching

Introduction

The transition from theory to practice is a critical component in the development of effective educators. While knowledge of pedagogy and content forms the foundation of teacher education, the ability to translate that knowledge into meaningful classroom practice distinguishes a proficient teacher from a novice. For preservice teachers (PSTs), bridging this gap requires more than coursework; it necessitates deliberate, supported, and situated practice. Practicum-based learning experiences have long served this role, allowing PSTs to build confidence, refine classroom management skills, and implement instructional strategies in authentic settings. However, access to high-quality practicum experiences can be inconsistent due to constraints such as school placement availability, variability in mentor teacher quality, and the high-stakes nature of live classroom environments. Additionally, practicums may not always be able to provide opportunities to practice classroom management skills needed for more challenging behaviors (Hudson et al., 2018).

Emerging technologies, particularly extended reality (XR) platforms, offer promising solutions to these challenges. XR platforms such as TeachLivE, Unity 3D, and Mursion have been increasingly integrated into teacher education programs, yielding positive results for self-efficacy, classroom management skills, and subject-specific knowledge (Wang & Li, 2024). Simulation platforms such as Mursion are gaining traction in teacher preparation programs for their ability to create low-risk, high-fidelity microteaching experiences. Mursion leverages mixed reality technology to simulate classroom interactions using human-controlled avatars, providing PSTs with opportunities to engage in authentic teaching tasks. These simulations replicate

the complexity and unpredictability of real classrooms while offering a safe space for experimentation, reflection, and iterative learning (Hudson et al., 2018). In this way, Mursion functions as a transitional practicum, supporting PSTs as they move from theoretical knowledge toward confident instructional practice (Landon-Hays et al., 2020). Mursion, serving this function, has a growing body of research that demonstrates its positive impact on PST preparedness.

Literature Review

Research indicates that Mursion has been shown to increase the self-efficacy of both general and special education PSTs in teaching by providing practice opportunities that help reduce their nervousness, improve public speaking skills, and hone their use of high-leverage practices (Ferguson & Sutphin, 2022; Peterson-Ahmad et al., 2023). In their 2022 study, Ferguson and Sutphin investigated the impact of Mursion micro-teaching on a group of 32 undergraduate PSTs who were enrolled in an introductory teaching course. They found that participating in the simulation helped the PSTs gain self-efficacy in teaching by providing them with an opportunity to practice their lessons and public speaking skills in a low-risk setting, which helped them overcome their nervousness about teaching.

In a similar study, Peterson-Ahmad et al. (2023) investigated how using Mursion can support the preparation and self-efficacy of general and special education PSTs in using inclusive teaching strategies and collaborative practices. The study involved 36 graduate-level general and special education PSTs. Their results revealed a significant increase in self-efficacy scores for the PSTs, and increased depth in post-teaching reflections. They noted that the PSTs recognized their need to differentiate

instruction and how the repeated practice and feedback allowed them to intentionally refine their lesson plans and use more explicit instruction, model content, and provide scaffolds for student learning.

Evidence shows that Mursion can also boost PSTs' confidence and effective use of classroom management techniques (Hudson et al., 2018; Horn et al., 2023). In their 2019 study, Hudson et al. investigated the effects of using Mursion micro-teaching experiences with preservice teachers on their perceptions of readiness to manage a classroom. They evaluated Mursion's impact on 29 undergraduate special education PSTs who were enrolled in a classroom management course. Results revealed that PSTs value the opportunity to practice managing challenging behaviors and the safe virtual environment, as it fosters a heightened awareness of what skills they still need to learn to become competent teachers (Hudson et al., 2019).

Despite the benefits, it is important to note that previous studies have also identified challenges that PSTs had with using Mursion. According to Ferguson & Sutphin (2022), some PSTs found working with the virtual avatars to be intimidating or awkward. Some viewed the available duration for teaching sessions as too short. Others noted that the avatar's inability to perform certain actions limited their options for teaching strategies. For example, when PSTs used clapping as an attention grabber, the avatars could not use this gesture.

This body of research on Mursion demonstrates that it can be a useful tool for teacher preparation programs to enhance preservice teacher preparedness by boosting self-efficacy and improving skills and classroom management. However, a notable gap in the literature exists, as most of the studies have focused on general procedural skills rather than on Mursion's impact on content-specific instruction, such as reading.

To address this gap, this study explores the integration of Mursion into a teacher preparation program focused on reading instruction. Specifically, it examines how simulated teaching experiences can enhance PSTs' readiness to deliver reading-focused lessons and to adapt instruction in response to students' needs. Situated within the Reading Endorsement curriculum for students in English Education tracks, this research seeks to understand how Mursion simulations contribute to the development of pedagogical decision-making and adaptive expertise in reading instruction.

The study was guided by two research questions:

1. How did participating in a Mursion simulation prepare preservice teachers to teach a reading-focused lesson in the classroom?
2. How did participating in a Mursion simulation prepare preservice teachers for adjusting to instructional needs during reading instruction?

Methods

Participants and Setting

The participants in this study were 18 preservice teachers (PSTs) enrolled in an English education program at a large, public, research-intensive university in the southern U.S. As a part of this program, PSTs earn an English education degree, reading, and English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL) endorsements. These PSTs were enrolled in a foundation of reading course as part of the reading endorsement. This required course is designed to equip future educators with the knowledge and skills to develop reading comprehension, oral language, and fluency skills in their students. The course assignments emphasize the implementation of research-based

reading instruction to meet the diverse needs of all learners, including those with special needs and English language learners.

Mursion Simulation Activity

As part of a course assignment, preservice teachers (PSTs) collaborated in pairs to develop a reading lesson plan focusing on phonics, fluency, vocabulary, or comprehension. After receiving instructor feedback and refining their plans, each PST individually taught their lesson during a Mursion session. Mursion offers a diverse range of virtual simulations for microteaching experiences, developed in partnership with K-12 schools, research institutions, and non-profit organizations. Mursion's catalog spans from early childhood to high school scenarios, including specialized options for special education, educational leadership, and parent-teacher conferences.

For this study, PSTs engaged in a specific scenario: introducing new academic content to a group of five middle schooler avatars. These avatars were designed with unique personalities, histories, interpersonal relationships, and distinct academic and social strengths and needs. For instance, one female avatar was characterized as an introverted perfectionist who struggled with criticism but possessed excellent memory recall, often participating in trivia nights with her parents, and shared a close friendship with another student. PSTs received detailed resources outlining the characteristics of each avatar.

Each Mursion simulation began with a meeting between the PST and a Mursion facilitator. The facilitator provided an overview of the simulation mechanics and explained the capabilities and limitations of the avatar students. Following this orientation, PSTs had 15 minutes to deliver their chosen reading lesson to the five virtual middle schoolers. The avatars, controlled by a combination of the facilitator

and artificial intelligence, exhibited typical middle school behaviors such as raising hands, asking questions, appearing disengaged (e.g., going to sleep), and having side conversations. Beyond introducing reading content, PSTs were also tasked with managing these behaviors and maintaining student engagement. After completing their reading sessions, PSTs participated in a debriefing session with the facilitator, which included reflective questions about their experience. The Mursion sessions were also recorded, allowing PSTs to review their teaching and further reflect on the experience.

Instrument

For this study, qualitative data were gathered from PSTs' reflections following their Mursion microteaching experience. Their written reflection assignment consisted of the following seven questions:

1. Did you feel that participating in a Mursion simulation prepared you for instruction as a preservice teacher? If yes, why? If no, why?
2. Did you feel that participating in a Mursion simulation prepared you for adjusting instructional needs during reading instruction? Yes or no, and why?
3. What areas of teaching did the Mursion experience determine that you need to focus on?
4. Did the safe learning space that Mursion provides allow you to make mistakes and learn from them without jeopardizing student learning?
5. How did you feel about Mursion before and after the session?
6. Do the simulations replicate authentic teaching scenarios that helped bridge the gap between theory and practice?

7. How would you describe your self-efficacy (confidence) with teaching reading lessons before and after the Mursion training?

Data Analysis

PSTs' reflections were collected through the course Canvas site. PSTs signed consent forms for the reflection responses to be included as this study's qualitative data. The reflections were stripped of identifying information, assigned individual codenames (P1, P2, P3, etc.), and uploaded to qualitative analysis software, MAXQDA. Only the two researchers had access to this data. Peer debriefing is the process in which a qualitative researcher engages in regular discussions with a peer to examine the study's progress, methodological decisions, data analysis, emerging themes, and interpretations (Spall, 1998). The first author completed the qualitative analysis and performed peer debriefings with the second author through each phase of the analysis. The peer debriefer provided critical feedback, challenged assumptions, and explored alternative explanations, which helps reduce potential bias and enhances the credibility of the analysis.

Braun and Clarke's (2022) six steps for reflexive thematic analysis were used because they offer a structured yet adaptable method for qualitative data analysis, aiming to systematically uncover, organize, and interpret patterns of meaning within a dataset. The process began with Phase 1: Familiarizing Yourself with the Data, which involved deep immersion through repeated readings of the participants' reflections. This was followed by Phase 2: Coding, where data segments were systematically labeled using a combination of deductive codes, guided by research questions, and inductive codes, which allow for the emergence of unexpected patterns (Merriam, 1998).

The following phases involved developing and refining those codes into meaningful themes. Phase 3: Generating Initial Themes focused on clustering related codes into preliminary "candidate themes" (Braun & Clarke, 2022). In Phase 4: Developing and Reviewing Themes, these candidate themes were evaluated for coherence and accuracy against the entire dataset, leading to multiple rounds of revisions, combinations, or discarding. This is also the phase where member checking was completed with the participants in order to enhance rigor. Member checking, also known as participant validation (Braun & Clarke, 2022), was conducted to verify the accuracy of the preliminary data analysis and ensure that the findings resonate with the PSTs' experiences. The first author came to the second author's class (which was made up of the PST participants) and presented a slide deck with preliminary analysis results. PSTs were invited to provide feedback on whether the analysis accurately reflected their experiences and perspectives. All of their feedback was carefully considered, and the analysis was revised as appropriate to incorporate participants' perspectives and enhance the validity of the findings. A record of the feedback and any resulting changes was maintained to document this process. Phase 5: Refining, Defining, and Naming Themes involved clearly articulating content and essence while assigning them a concise and evocative name. Finally, Phase 6: Writing Up, involved constructing a narrative that presents the identified themes, supported by evidence from the data, and offering insights relevant to the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2022).

Positionality

For qualitative researchers, it's important to acknowledge how positionality influences every stage of the qualitative research process (Kim, 2024). Various

aspects of researchers' identities, including gender, educational background, and professional experience, inherently shape perspectives and can impact interpretations and interactions with participants. The first author completed the qualitative analysis.

His professional background includes four years as a special education teacher. This experience, particularly during the transition to online and hybrid learning environments due to COVID-19, highlighted the significant potential of technology to deliver individualized and engaging instruction. It also made him acutely aware of the time and resource constraints faced by educators and families. This dual awareness has deeply informed his research interests, driving him to explore and develop more efficient and effective methods for individualized learning, especially through technological solutions.

His passion for understanding how educators can best leverage technology to enhance learning experiences, as seen in the Mursion simulations, is a direct extension of this commitment. To mitigate potential bias stemming from his positionality and ensure a more objective and nuanced analysis, he committed to demonstrating reflexivity throughout this study. This was accomplished through engaging in peer debriefing with the second author throughout all stages of analysis to critically examine his interpretations and assumptions.

Results

The thematic analysis of PSTs' reflections on their Mursion microteaching experience revealed four key themes illustrating the impact of the simulation on their teaching preparedness and pedagogical growth. The first two themes directly addressed the research questions, identified through deductive coding. The third and fourth themes emerged inductively from the

data. These themes include: "Preparation to Teach," discussing how the experience enhanced their confidence and readiness for the classroom; "Reflections on Adjusting Classroom Management and Instruction," which captures PSTs' insights into adapting their teaching strategies; "Mursion is a Safe Space," which highlights the low-stakes environment for practice and feedback; and "Authentic Versus Inauthentic Teaching Experience," detailing the polarized perceptions of realism within the simulation. Each theme is explored below, supported by illustrative participant quotes.

Preparation to Teach

The Mursion simulation significantly contributed to PSTs' perceived readiness for teaching, with 44 statements highlighting how the experience enhanced their overall preparedness. A recurring sentiment was that the experience substantially increased their confidence in teaching. For example, one PST stated, "It made me feel well off with teaching and more confident with the practices I have been taught." Specifically concerning reading instruction, another PST noted, "After the Mursion training, I would say that I have much more confidence with teaching reading lessons." Successfully delivering a lesson in the virtual simulator often represented a significant achievement for some PSTs, as encapsulated by this statement: "I feel more prepared to administer reading instruction than I did before because I was able to see success without any pressure."

The opportunity to apply pedagogical knowledge gained during their teacher preparation program within a safe, simulated environment helped many PSTs increase their self-efficacy. For instance, one PST commented, "It also helped me improve upon my lesson plan so I feel more confident presenting it in an actual classroom." Another observed, "I basically just put into practice what I've learned so

far, and it seemed to go pretty well." Furthermore, several PSTs noted that the virtual teaching experience effectively decreased their anxiety about teaching real-world students. One PST specifically stated, "[Mursion] allowed me to lose some anxieties I have surrounding teaching in general." For some PSTs, the Mursion simulation marked their first independent teaching experience. It provided a solo opportunity that significantly built their confidence in becoming autonomous educators. For example, one PST expressed, "The simulation did build my confidence overall with delivering a Lesson [sic] plan all by myself since I have always had at least one other person alongside me." The ability to practice their lesson plans in Mursion also allowed PSTs to refine them before implementation with real-world students. One PST emphasized this by saying, "Mursion serves as a practice for a lesson plan, and it can help you make noticeable changes when carrying it over into our real-world classrooms."

Reflections on Adjusting Classroom Instruction and Management

The Mursion experience consistently prompted PSTs to reflect on how they either adjusted or should adjust their instructional practices and classroom management during teaching. This theme encompasses two key areas of reflection: adapting instruction and refining classroom management. PSTs made 18 statements detailing how Mursion provided an opportunity to practice adjusting instruction. For instance, one PST noted, "At one point, the student Ethan (avatar) was starting to fall asleep, and Ava went on her phone. I knew that I needed to engage them in a different way from what I was already doing to encourage more participation." Others described how the experience allowed them to modify their questioning frequency or the pace of their lectures. One PST stated, "This taught me to

adapt my instruction by asking the students more questions to ensure they understand the material and to slow down my lesson so that it doesn't become repetitive." Some PSTs also identified areas where they could reduce the amount of support provided. For example, a PST said, "I was able to realize that I perhaps included too much modeling during my lesson. I could tell that the students were losing interest, and that they were all ready to attempt working on the activity together as a class."

The simulation also prompted some PSTs to consider introducing new strategies to support student learning. One PST remarked, "I found that I needed to provide more tangible and visual resources to help lessons run more smoothly." While some PSTs felt the experience did not help them adjust instruction, others recognized specific skills requiring further development, such as presenting new information. One PST stated, "I do acknowledge that I need to improve my presentation skills in order to run a smooth classroom." In the context of reading instruction, the Mursion experience helped some PSTs realize the importance of leveraging students' background knowledge. One PST stated, "The biggest area of teaching that Mursion experience helped me determine is that I need to focus on connecting to background knowledge." Another described that they learned the importance of incorporating familiar topics to tap into students' prior knowledge and connect learning to their own experiences.

Regarding classroom management, PSTs made 34 statements reflecting on how the Mursion simulation prompted their consideration of this critical area. Many realized through the experience that classroom management was an area they needed to focus on, with one student noting, "Another thing I notice is that I need to grow to become more confident in my ability to teach as well as my abilities to manage a

classroom." A significant concern for many was time management, as several ran out of time before completing prepared tasks. For example, one PST stated, "I believe the biggest issue I had during the simulation that I will need to adjust for the future is time management." This prompted some to reconsider how they plan to deliver new material in chunks. Others recognized the need to distribute their attention equally among students. One PST described how, during the debrief with the Mursion facilitator, they were advised, "I need to balance my attachment to each student so they don't fall behind." Conversely, some PSTs reported that the experience boosted their confidence in their classroom management skills. One PST confidently stated, "I felt good about being able to manage the classroom." Another stated, "After the exercise, I feel more confident that I can use classroom management techniques in the field and navigate student behaviors and interests."

Mursion is a Safe Space

A significant majority of PSTs described the Mursion microteaching experience as a safe space for practicing their teaching skills. This theme emerged from 27 distinct comments, encompassing various facets of the "safe space" concept. Many PSTs highlighted how interacting with and practicing teaching alongside the virtual avatars fostered a secure environment for skill development. Others specifically mentioned the helpful feedback provided by Mursion facilitators as a boost to their confidence. Furthermore, some PSTs expressed such enjoyment that they desired more Mursion experiences.

A prominent reason cited for this sense of safety was the low-stakes nature of the virtual classroom, where PSTs felt comfortable making mistakes without fear of causing educational harm to students. One PST articulated this, stating, "Through

Mursion, no one's lives are being affected, and if I mess up, there are no repercussions." The perceived lack of permanent consequences for their instructional choices appeared to empower them to experiment with new strategies learned during coursework. Many PSTs had previously expressed anxiety about potential "rookie teacher" mistakes jeopardizing student learning. However, the Mursion simulation provided an invaluable opportunity to practice these skills without the worry of negatively impacting student learning or their own academic progress within the program. For example, one PST noted, "it just allowed me to feel more comfortable knowing if I made mistakes it wouldn't harm me or my students' learning."

The avatars themselves contributed to this supportive environment; when PSTs faltered or corrected themselves, the avatars responded with kindness and understanding, further solidifying a comforting space for practice. This judgment-free zone was highly valued, as one PST commented, "I do believe that this experience has helped me as a pre-service teacher because it allowed me to practice and use certain strategies that we've talked about within a class and a judgment-free zone." While some PSTs initially felt uncomfortable or nervous in the virtual environment, many reported feeling more at ease as the lesson progressed. One PST shared, "I did not feel adequately prepared for the task that I was about to embark on, but as I started talking to the simulation, I got more comfortable and felt a confident boost as I was interacting with the students."

Another key aspect contributing to the safe space was the "practice sandwich" structure of the Mursion experience. This involved an introductory meeting with the Mursion facilitator before the microteaching session and a follow-up debriefing session afterward, where the facilitator provided

targeted feedback. As one student observed, "meeting with the simulated advisor before and after the lesson acted as a wonderful practice sandwich, causing me to pay closer attention to my performance going into the lesson, and then better reflecting on my strengths, weaknesses, and general impression after the fact." Facilitators offered PSTs specific feedback, for instance, on areas like time management, and effectively prompted PSTs to reflect on their own teaching.

While some PSTs initially experienced discomfort with the virtual facilitator, this unease often dissipated with exposure. One PST noted, "when the avatar instructor first came on to the screen, it was a little weird since it was hard to comprehend that there was a real person talking to me, not just an AI generated robot. However, as we talked more, I felt more comfortable and he eased my nerves before the actual lesson presentation began." This facilitative feedback mirrors the immediate guidance PSTs receive from their education professors during in-field teaching experiences.

The perceived positive nature of the Mursion experience led some PSTs to desire additional sessions and recommend it to other aspiring teachers. One PST asserted, "I would recommend for aspiring teachers to use this program as it gives a low-stakes, high-reward opportunity to test out lessons, techniques, and general classroom management skills." Reasons for this desire included wanting to practice with students exhibiting more challenging behaviors and experiencing a wider variety of classroom situations to enhance preparedness. As one PST stated, "I would like to continue the simulation again on a harder level to feel even more prepared for any situations that may take place within the classroom before actually becoming a teacher and having to deal with these situations without

experiencing them." Others specifically wished for longer sessions, with one PST commenting, "I wish this session wasn't as short as it was, because I would have loved to continue practicing." These sentiments underscore the PSTs' strong desire for more opportunities to practice their skills, highlighting how virtual microteaching spaces like Mursion effectively address this need.

Authentic Versus Inauthentic Teaching Experience

The authenticity of the Mursion microteaching experience elicited polarized opinions among PSTs. A primary source of this contention stemmed from the nature of the student avatars themselves. While some PSTs perceived teaching the avatars as authentic, others felt that the avatars' lack of genuine student characteristics led to inauthentic teaching. Additionally, some students noted that inherent limitations within the Mursion virtual environment impacted their instructional capabilities.

For PSTs who found the Mursion experience authentic, many highlighted that despite the avatars being "fake", their appearance and behaviors accurately mirrored observations from real classrooms. For instance, one PST commented, "The situation I was put in during the simulation did feel authentic to what I've seen and experienced in the field thus far." The diverse personalities and quirks displayed by the avatars were frequently cited as contributing to this sense of realism. As one PST put it, "the experience was more accurate to an actual classroom experience with students of different personalities, which helped bridge the gap in my learning between theory and actual practice." Furthermore, given that the simulation scenario established the PST as the avatars' existing teacher, the avatars behaved as if they already knew the PST, leading one PST to state, "at times, the artificial students

actually gave me more of an authentic experience than the students I see in the field since the artificial students treated me as though I had been their teacher all year." The realistic reactions of the avatars were so compelling that PSTs felt rewarded when their teaching strategies proved effective. For example, one PST observed, "it was very rewarding to see the student engaging with the lesson during the think pair share time and displaying an understanding of learning new vocabulary words using the skills that I had taught them."

Conversely, some PSTs found it challenging to overlook the simulated nature of the experience, which detracted from its perceived authenticity. One PST stated, "The issue I found is that since I knew Mursion was a simulation, I felt that my responses and instructions were not entirely authentic." The absence of real students led some to believe that, despite its value, Mursion could not truly replicate an actual classroom. This sentiment was encapsulated by one PST who remarked, "I think there's value in it, but I am viewing it more like an indoor track at the gym, good for practicing but still very different from running outside against other athletes." The student avatars themselves were often identified as the source of these feelings of inauthenticity, with some describing them as "creepy." One PST admitted, "Before going into Mursion, I found the simulated students to be weird and honestly quite hard to look at without being freaked out."

Moreover, multiple PSTs identified specific limitations within the Mursion environment that hindered their teaching abilities. A common concern was the restricted teaching time (e.g., 15 minutes), which often left them feeling they needed more time to delve deeply into their lessons. Other, more specific issues included the absence of a screen-sharing feature from the teacher's perspective and the confined space

for interacting with the virtual avatars (who could only remain at their desks). One PST lamented, "I also didn't like that I couldn't use some of the resources [screensharing] that I usually take advantage of." Given that a primary instructional goal was to teach reading skills, some PSTs felt that the avatars' limitations prevented them from engaging in as comprehensive a reading instruction as they desired.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explore how Mursion simulation experiences prepare preservice teachers (PSTs) to teach reading-focused lessons, particularly in their ability to adjust instruction in response to student needs. Although the findings were limited, they confirmed that Mursion served as a valuable tool for bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application by providing a tailored opportunity for deliberate practice. The results indicated that PSTs experienced increased self-efficacy and confidence, which prompted critical reflection on both their pedagogical skills and the broader instructional practices they have learned throughout their teacher preparation program.

Benefits

Increase Self-Efficacy and Pedagogical Development

A key takeaway was that, for most participants, the Mursion micro-teaching experience enhanced their self-efficacy in teaching reading. Many PSTs described how the simulation helped them bridge the gap between coursework and practical application, allowing them to apply content knowledge and instructional strategies in a realistic setting. The experience also encouraged deeper reflection on reading pedagogical practices, such as the importance of activating students'

background knowledge during reading instruction. The Mursion session highlighted the value of explicit instruction and thorough preparation. One participant shared that the experience emphasized “the importance of really knowing your content.” This experience led many of the PSTs to realize the need for a comprehensive understanding of content. For example, the ability to address multiple definitions of a vocabulary word. One PST was caught off guard when an avatar offered a definition they hadn’t anticipated, reinforcing the need to be fully prepared for a range of student responses.

Impact on Adjusting Instruction and Classroom Management

A major takeaway in this study is that Mursion effectively pushes PSTs beyond simple lesson delivery, compelling them to reflect on and adjust their instructional and classroom management strategies in the moment. The Mursion micro-teaching experience made PSTs acutely aware of student engagement, prompting them to adapt their lessons when they notice students becoming distracted or losing interest. PSTs noted that the simulation provided a valuable opportunity to practice modifying their lecturing pace and questioning frequency in the moment. It also helped them recognize the importance of instructional scaffolds, such as adjusting the amount of modeling they used or incorporating visual supports. A particularly significant takeaway for reading instruction was their acknowledgement of the need to tap into students’ background knowledge to connect new material to their prior experiences.

The focus on in-the-moment adaptation was particularly evident in the context of classroom management, where the limited time forced PSTs to confront the challenges of time management directly. The simulation caused PSTs to quickly

realize how conversations could veer off topic and how much instructional time could be lost to small interruptions. This led to a greater appreciation for thorough preparation, reinforcing that effective time management is foundational for successful teaching. The experience highlighted the importance of being organized, having materials ready, and beginning lessons efficiently to maximize every moment of instructional time.

Mursion Is a Safe, Low-Stakes Environment

Mursion provides PSTs a safe space to practice their teaching skills. A key takeaway from both participants’ experiences and our observations was that the simulation offers a secure space for PSTs to experiment with new instructional strategies learned in their coursework without the risk of negatively impacting actual student learning. This was especially valuable for PSTs teaching independently for the first time. Additionally, Mursion addresses several limitations of traditional practicum settings, such as inconsistent access to school placements and limited exposure to diverse student populations. For instance, the simulation allowed PSTs to engage with avatars intentionally designed with specific characteristics, including those representing English language learners. This ensured they had the opportunity to apply targeted teaching strategies and receive meaningful feedback, experiences that are not always guaranteed in real-world classroom placements.

Limitations and Recommendations

While the overall experience was positive, participants identified several limitations within the Mursion platform. One major concern was the 30-minute session length, which many felt was insufficient, especially since the first eight to nine minutes were often used for facilitator instructions. As a result, PSTs had limited

time to deliver full or even partial lessons. This echoes similar challenges faced in previous research of PSTs using Mursion (Ferguson & Sutphin, 2022). A potential improvement could involve Mursion offering pre-recorded instructional videos or conducting a separate pre-conference meeting before the session. This would allow the full session to be devoted to teaching. Additionally, extending individual session lengths to 45 or 60 minutes would enable PSTs to work through more complete lessons, providing a more authentic and productive practice experience closer to what they will encounter in real classrooms.

As with the previous Mursion studies (Ferguson & Sutphin, 2022), some PSTs found avatars to be “awkward” or “creepy” initially; however, for most, exposure to the virtual environment helped to ease these issues. However, another limitation they identified was the avatars' restricted interactivity with reading materials, especially concerning what they could read on screen. One participant noted that the avatars “can’t read anything on our screen”, referring to the absence of a screen-sharing function with online materials. Integrating a screen-sharing feature would allow PSTs to present online instructional materials similar to how they would during remote instruction or when using a smart board in the classroom. Given the widespread use of screen-sharing technology, this addition would significantly enhance the simulation’s authenticity.

Future Research Directions

Building on these findings, several areas for future research emerged. One potential study would be to conduct a comparative study between Mursion micro-teaching and traditional peer-to-peer role-play simulations. Such a study could quantitatively assess differences in self-efficacy and the application of evidence-based instructional strategies.

Although most current Mursion research focuses on preservice teachers, the platform may also benefit in-service educators. Future studies could explore how incorporating Mursion into school district first-year teacher programs or programs that support the professional development of first-year and/or veteran teachers by offering structured practice in a low-stakes environment during a critical phase of their career.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Mursion simulation experience is a valuable and impactful component of teacher preparation programs. It offers a safe, tailored, and reflective space for preservice teachers to grow professionally. The simulation not only reinforced PSTs' understanding of reading instruction but also promoted critical reflection on essential teaching skills such as classroom management, instructional planning, and adaptability. By bridging the gap between theory and practice, Mursion serves as a powerful tool in preparing more confident, competent, and reflective educators ready to meet the challenges of today’s classrooms.

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